

Exploring Multidimensional Approaches to Combat Gastric Cancer

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Abstract

Cancer is a broad term that refers to a group of diseases characterized by uncontrolled cell growth and division. Gastric cancer, also known as stomach cancer, is the fifth most common cancer and the third leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide. The incidence and mortality rates of gastric cancer vary significantly across different regions. Dietary modifications and smoking cessation show promise for the prevention of gastric cancer, while advances in genetic testing facilitate early detection, leading to improved survival rates. In this study, we explore various approaches in the fields of prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of gastric cancer. Furthermore, we examine the role of lifestyle factors and emerging therapies in enhancing patient outcomes.

Keywords: Cancer, Gastric cancer, Prevention, Diagnosis, Treatment.

1. Introduction

The stomach is lined with a mucous membrane composed of columnar epithelial cells and glands. These cells are susceptible to inflammation, a condition known as gastritis, which can lead to the development of stomach ulcers and, ultimately, gastric cancer [1]. Gastric adenocarcinomas are primarily classified into two categories—cardiac and non-cardiac—based on their anatomical location. Gastric cardia cancers arise in the region adjacent to the esophageal-gastric junction, sharing epidemiological features with esophageal adenocarcinoma (EAC). Non-cardia cancer, also referred to as distal gastric cancer, is more prevalent and occurs in the lower part of the stomach [2].

Histologically, gastric cancer is categorized into two main types: diffuse and intestinal. Diagnosis is typically achieved through histological examination following an endoscopic biopsy, and staging is performed using various imaging techniques, including CT scans, endoscopic ultrasound, PET scans, and laparoscopy. Gastric cancer is a highly heterogeneous disease at both the molecular and phenotypic levels, presenting numerous challenges in the fields of molecular biology and genetics. Additionally,

understanding the underlying mechanisms of this disease is crucial for developing targeted therapies.

2. Epidemiology

Stomach cancer is a significant health concern worldwide. Due to the advanced stages at which stomach cancer is often diagnosed, the mortality rate is high, making it the third most common cause of cancer-related deaths. The highest incidence and mortality rates for stomach cancer are observed in East Asia, Eastern Europe, and South America. The incidence of stomach cancer in men is approximately twice that of women [1]. Despite a continuous decline in the incidence and mortality rates of this cancer over the past century, health professionals can expect to see more cases in the future due to an aging population. Improvements in living conditions associated with economic development have contributed to a reduction in the prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori*, the primary causative agent of stomach cancer.

Globally, the incidence of gastric cancer has steadily decreased over the past 50 years. These declines are consistently linked to the successful reduction of *H. pylori* infections and are likely due

to changes in food storage practices, including reduced pickling of vegetables, less smoking, and changes in meat processing. This decrease is also attributed to greater availability of fresh fruits and vegetables. Another critical factor in reducing stomach cancer incidence has been the success of prevention and treatment strategies targeting *Helicobacter pylori* infection, particularly in many developing countries. Approximately 90% of non-cardia gastric cancer cases are associated with *H. pylori*, which explains the decline in the incidence of this subtype as infection rates fall. In East Asia, the decreasing prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* has led to a reduction in non-cardia gastric cancer rates. However, Latin America has not seen a similarly effective campaign against *H. pylori*, which means that the risk of gastric cancer will remain high in the foreseeable future [3].

Additionally, stomach cancer survival rates have steadily improved over the past 40 years, thanks to advancements in early detection and better treatment options.

3. Risk Factors

3-1. Genetics

Inherited mutations in certain genes, such as the *CDH1* gene, significantly increase the risk of stomach cancer. The loss of one copy of the *CDH1* gene is linked to hereditary diffuse gastric cancer (HDGC), an autosomal dominant condition characterized by the spread of malignant cells beneath the stomach lining, ultimately leading to metastasis. HDGC and *CDH1* loss are also associated with an increased risk of lobular breast cancer, prostate cancer, and colorectal cancer [4].

Gastric adenocarcinoma and proximal gastric polyp syndrome (GAPPS) represent another cancer-prone condition inherited in an autosomal dominant pattern. Point mutations in the *APC* promoter result in the loss of the wild-type allele in fundic gland polyps. Additionally, familial adenomatous polyposis (FAP), the most common form of hereditary gastrointestinal cancer, is an autosomal dominant disorder characterized by a predisposition to adenomatous polyps, which is caused by germline mutations in the *APC* gene [5]. Furthermore, the interplay between genetic predisposition and environmental factors remains crucial in understanding the full spectrum of risk for developing gastric cancer.

3-1-1. Chromosomal Instability in Gastric Cancer

According to the Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA), gastric cancers can be classified into four molecular subtypes: Epstein-Barr virus positive (EBV+), microsatellite instability (MSI), chromosomal instability (CIN), and genomically stable tumors [6]. This proposed molecular classification aims to facilitate research targeted at improving the diagnosis and treatment of gastric cancer patients. However, some molecular subtypes, including the CIN subtype, have not been adequately characterized and currently lack reliable markers for molecular and histological confirmation.

Malignant tumors are characterized by a heightened level of abnormal genomic alterations known as genomic instability, which includes MSI and CIN. Both types of instability contribute to the tumor's mutant phenotype [7].

MSI is defined by mutations that commonly occur in regions of microsatellite repeats and are associated with genetic or epigenetic changes in genes encoding the mismatch repair (MMR) proteins MSH2, MSH6, PMS2, and MLH1 [8].

In contrast, chromosomal instability (CIN) refers to the spatial and temporal changes in the structure or number of chromosomes that arise during carcinogenesis. These chromosomal changes are linked to tumor growth and may serve as mechanisms for cellular adaptation to the alterations associated with malignant transformation. Approximately 80% of human tumors exhibit chromosomal abnormalities that may indicate the presence of CIN [9].

Loss of genetic material from the short arm of chromosome 1 has been associated with increased tumor aggressiveness and poor prognosis for patients [10]. Similarly, loss of the long arm of chromosome 5 correlates with a more aggressive phenotype, lymph node metastasis, and unfavorable outcomes in patients with gastric cancer. Gains in the long arm of chromosome 8, the most common aberrations observed in the CIN subtype of gastric cancer, have been shown to promote cell proliferation, invasion, and tumor progression due to the activation of oncogenes located on this chromosome [11].

Other chromosomal abnormalities frequently seen in the gastric cancer CIN subtype include copy number increases in the long and short arms of chromosome 20. These duplicated regions on chromosome 20 encompass several functionally significant genes involved in cell cycle regulation, DNA methylation, chromatin remodeling, and transcription [12]. Furthermore, understanding the patterns of chromosomal instability may provide critical insights for developing targeted therapies and improving patient outcomes in gastric cancer.

3-2. Epstein-Barr Virus (EBV)

Approximately 5 to 10 percent of gastric carcinomas are associated with Epstein-Barr virus (EBV). One study found that EBV-related stomach cancer is twice as common in men as in women. Additionally, EBV-associated gastric cancer is more frequently found in the gastric ventricle or in the region of the gastric stump following surgery. Recent studies have demonstrated that co-infection with EBV and *Helicobacter pylori* significantly increases the incidence of gastric carcinoma [13].

3-3. *Helicobacter pylori*

Lifestyle factors and stress have historically been considered the main risk factors for peptic ulcer disease. However, in 1985, Barry Marshall famously infected himself with *Helicobacter pylori* to illustrate that it causes acute gastritis. Thanks to their groundbreaking work, we now understand that up to 80% of gastric ulcers are attributable to this bacterium [14].

Moreover, gastritis caused by *H. pylori* is implicated in the majority of stomach cancers, with approximately 90% of non-cardia gastric cancer cases associated with this bacterium. In fact, *H. pylori* has been found to increase the odds ratio of developing stomach cancer by 5.9 times within ten years of infection. Polymorphisms in interleukin genes, specifically IL-10 and IL-

17, have been shown to interact with *H. pylori* infection, potentially influencing the risk of gastric cancer. Recent studies also suggest that the Cardia subtype of gastric cancer has two distinct etiologies: one resembling esophageal adenocarcinoma (EAC), which is predominantly *H. pylori* negative, and the other similar to non-cardia cancer [15]. Genome sequencing and post-genomic analyses of *H. pylori* indicate a long history of co-evolution with the human host. Understanding these interactions is crucial for developing targeted prevention and treatment strategies against gastric cancer.

3-4. Acid Reflux Disease and Its Association with Esophageal Cancer

Several studies have reported a significant association between gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and gastric cardia cancer. This type of cancer has been positively linked to both severe gastric atrophy and frequent GERD symptoms [16]. There are various distinct pathways of tumorigenesis at the gastroesophageal junction, one of which involves the development of tumors from intestinal dysplastic metaplasia, while another may be associated with cardiac-type mucosal dysplasia. Notably, the incidence of reflux-related cardiac cancer has steadily increased in comparison to *Helicobacter pylori*-related cardiac cancer. The trends in the incidence rates of reflux-related cardiac cancer and esophageal adenocarcinoma are quite similar, suggesting that these two cancers share a common etiology and pathophysiological process [17]. Understanding these connections is essential for the development of effective prevention and treatment strategies for patients at risk of gastric and esophageal cancers.

3-5. Environmental Factors

Environmental factors such as diet, obesity, smoking, alcohol consumption, and exposure to chemicals can significantly contribute to the occurrence of stomach cancer. Studies on tobacco have shown that tobacco use increases the risk of developing stomach cancer, which is correlated with the recent rise in stomach cancer incidence in developed countries. It is estimated that 11% of gastric cancers worldwide and 17% of cases in Europe are related to smoking [2].

Alcohol consumption also increases the risk of stomach cancer; however, the effect of the amount of alcohol consumed remains controversial. One study indicates that moderate alcohol consumption increases the risk of stomach cancer by 39%, while another study finds no connection between moderate alcohol intake and gastric cancer risk. Nevertheless, the positive association between gastric cancer and alcohol consumption continues to be explored [18]. Alcohol can irritate and erode the gastric mucosa, leading to gastritis, a known precursor to gastric cancer [19].

Exposure to dust, high-temperature particles, and metals such as chromium also contributes to non-cardiac gastric cancer. Various occupations, including wood processing, food machinery, rubber manufacturing, coal mining, and metal processing, have been identified as having a higher risk for neoplasms. Additionally, high salt consumption exacerbates gastritis and enhances the carcinogenic effects of known gastric carcinogens, such as N-

methyl N-nitro-N-nitrosoguanidine (MNNG). Salt erodes the mucous barrier of the stomach, leading to inflammation. Cultures with high-salt diets, including those that consume pickled foods, such as the Japanese, exhibit higher stomach cancer rates. Notably, Japanese immigrants to the United States who adopted Western diets experienced significantly lower rates of stomach cancer than those who maintained their traditional diets.

Canned meats, which are rich in N-nitroso compounds, can also create similar effects within the body. Grain-fed red meat is particularly high in saturated fats while being low in protective fats like omega-3 fatty acids. Obesity may be influenced by inflammatory markers such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1), all of which contribute to inflammation of the stomach lining. Individuals with diets high in inflammatory foods, especially those rich in meat and low in fruits and vegetables, face an increased risk of obesity [20].

Furthermore, studies indicate that individuals with pernicious anemia have a 6.9% chance of developing stomach cancer, particularly non-cardiac cancer, which is over five times higher than the general population. The precise relationship between pernicious anemia and gastric cancer remains unclear. Chronic gastritis, often caused by *Helicobacter pylori* infection, may result from long-term use of proton pump inhibitors (PPIs), which can reduce vitamin B12 absorption and lead to pernicious anemia [21]. These environmental factors contribute to the inflammatory processes within the stomach and consequently increase the risk of stomach cancer. Additionally, environmental awareness and lifestyle modifications may play a crucial role in reducing stomach cancer risk, emphasizing the importance of preventive measures in at-risk populations.

4. Prevention

General measures to reduce the risk of stomach cancer align with recommendations for lowering cancer risk overall. These measures include smoking cessation, limited alcohol consumption, and dietary modifications (e.g., salt restriction and increasing fruit and vegetable intake). Cumulative data from a wide range of studies indicate that the eradication of *Helicobacter pylori* significantly reduces the risk of stomach cancer, particularly in individuals with chronic gastritis. However, population-based treatment of healthy individuals with antibiotic regimens for *H. pylori* is impractical and may lead to adverse effects related to antibiotic resistance and alterations in the microbiome. Therefore, treatment for *H. pylori* as a preventive measure should be individualized based on specific risk factors and clinical considerations.

5. Screening

There are significant regional differences in the incidence of gastric cancer. For instance, Japan and South Korea have implemented national stomach cancer screening programs. Screening for stomach cancer typically includes radiography and endoscopy. Other non-invasive methods, such as measuring serum pepsinogen levels, *Helicobacter pylori* serology, and serum trefoil factor 3, have also been explored, although their utility remains controversial. Further studies are necessary to establish

the effectiveness and role of these non-invasive gastric cancer screening methods. In addition, increasing public awareness and access to screening programs might enhance early detection rates, ultimately improving outcomes for individuals at higher risk for gastric cancer.

6. Diagnosis

Gastric cancer is generally classified based on diagnosis and treatment into three categories: early gastric cancer (EGC), operable gastric cancer, and advanced gastric cancer. EGC is an aggressive form of gastric cancer that affects the mucosa and submucosa, regardless of lymph node metastasis. Endoscopy is the preferred treatment for EGC, with a 5-year survival rate exceeding 90%. Operable gastric cancer is defined as a resectable, locally advanced tumor, whereas advanced gastric cancer refers to inoperable, locally advanced, or metastatic disease.

Clinical manifestations of gastric cancer can vary widely among individuals and may be nonspecific, ranging from mild dyspepsia to significant obstructive symptoms indicative of advanced disease. The most common signs and symptoms include indigestion, anorexia, early satiety, weight loss, abdominal pain, and anemia. Diagnosis is typically made through endoscopic examination, during which the tumor's location in the stomach and its macroscopic type are assessed, followed by a biopsy for histological confirmation. Clinical staging is critical in determining whether the treatment approach will be curative or palliative.

Despite advances in understanding the biology of gastric cancer, surgical or endoscopic resection remains the cornerstone of treatment with curative intent. In recent decades, the field of gastric cancer surgery has been dominated by two main issues: the debate regarding the optimal extent of lymphadenectomy and the rapid development of digital technology and screen-based interventional techniques. These advancements have led to minimally invasive interventions, such as endoscopic mucosal resection for early gastric cancer and laparoscopic and robotic gastrectomy techniques for both early and advanced gastric cancer.

Biomarkers for targeted therapies are rapidly evolving. Key biomarkers include microsatellite instability (MSI) or mismatch repair deficiency (dMMR) in all patients, along with HER2 and PD-L1 expression in M1 disease. Additional biomarkers, such as high tumor mutational load, NTRK gene fusions, and Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) status, may also emerge in the near future. Next-generation sequencing, when available, is suitable for comprehensive analyses rather than individual assays. Finally, circulating tumor DNA offers valuable diagnostic and monitoring information for patient management.

7. Treatment

Endoscopic ultrasound and computed tomography (CT) are typically employed during the staging evaluation of gastric cancer. Gastrectomy and adjuvant therapy are considered for cases with a high probability of nodal involvement or those requiring non-therapeutic resection. Originally developed in East Asia, endoscopic techniques have gained sufficient expertise in

the United States, Europe, and Latin America at specialized centers of excellence [22].

Data comparing endoscopic resection to endoscopic mucosal resection indicate that the former yields a higher rate of complete and histological resection, curative resection, and a lower risk of local recurrence. However, endoscopy demands more time and clinical expertise [23]. Lesions smaller than 1 cm may be suitable for endoscopic mucosal resection. Some experts recommend endoscopic block resection for high-grade dysplasia and low-grade dysplasia characterized by mucosal irregularity [24]. Additionally, the integration of multidisciplinary teams in treatment planning can enhance patient outcomes, ensuring that each patient's therapeutic approach is tailored to their specific condition and needs.

7-1. Operable Gastric Cancer

Targeted therapies are rapidly evolving, and based on ongoing clinical trials, they may soon become first-line treatments for operable gastric cancer, particularly in patients with specific biomarkers such as microsatellite instability (MSI), mismatch repair deficiency (dMMR), HER2, and PD-L1 status. Surgical interventions are classified into standard and non-standard gastrectomy. Standard gastrectomy typically involves the removal of two-thirds of the stomach, while non-standard gastrectomy encompasses various types of gastrectomy depending on the tumor stage.

7-2. Neoadjuvant/Perioperative Chemotherapy

Postoperative chemotherapy has become a cornerstone of treatment for locally advanced gastric cancer. Common regimens include FLOT (fluorouracil, folinic acid, oxaliplatin, and docetaxel) and ECF (epirubicin, cisplatin, and intravenous fluorouracil). Notably, data indicate an improvement in survival rates from 23% to 36% associated with intraoperative chemotherapy administered for 2 to 3 months.

Compared to ECF, the FLOT regimen has demonstrated a better pathological response, a higher R0 resection rate, and improved survival outcomes. As such, it is recommended as the standard of care for patients with locally advanced gastric cancer who are able to tolerate a combination regimen of three drugs postoperatively [26]. Additionally, ongoing research into biomarker-driven therapies and novel chemotherapy agents continues to be imperative in personalizing treatment approaches, ultimately leading to better patient outcomes.

7-3. Advanced Gastric Cancer

Chemotherapy and targeted therapies are the standard of care for patients with metastatic or locally advanced unresectable gastric cancer [27]. Palliative endoscopy or bypass surgery is usually indicated in specific situations, such as refractory bleeding or obstruction. Notably, the only published randomized controlled trial comparing chemotherapy to surgery plus chemotherapy demonstrated no significant survival benefit [28].

7-4. Chemotherapy After Surgery

Adjuvant chemotherapy is typically based on fluoropyrimidine, employing either monotherapy with S-1 (a combination of tegafur, gimeracil, and oteracil) or combination therapy with capecitabine and oxaliplatin, or S-1 and docetaxel. Adjuvant chemotherapy is considered the standard of care for Asian patients [29].

It is noteworthy that the prominent Asian studies demonstrating the effectiveness of adjuvant chemotherapy involved patients who had undergone lymphadenectomy [30]. In contrast, studies of adjuvant chemotherapy in non-Asian populations have not shown improved survival rates, partly due to a broader range of surgical interventions that did not consistently include lymphadenectomy. Furthermore, adjuvant chemotherapy is often less well tolerated than neoadjuvant chemotherapy, leading to a preference for postoperative approaches outside of Asia.

This strategy allows more patients to benefit from systemic therapy, even though the postoperative effects may not always be clearly presented. Additionally, ongoing investigations into optimizing chemotherapy regimens and refining surgical techniques continue to be crucial for improving outcomes in patients with advanced gastric cancer.

7-5. Anti-Angiogenic Treatment

Anti-angiogenic therapy with ramucirumab, an antibody targeting vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2 (VEGFR2), has demonstrated clinical utility both as a monotherapy and in combination with paclitaxel for patients with gastric cancer who have progressed after first-line chemotherapy. However, neither ramucirumab nor bevacizumab, which is an anti-VEGF monoclonal antibody, has shown an improvement in survival when used alongside platinum or fluoropyrimidine chemotherapy in patients with untreated advanced gastric cancer [31].

7-6. Immunotherapy for Patients with Advanced Gastric Cancer

Immune checkpoint blockade is being developed as a treatment option for chemoresistant gastric cancer, defined as cancer that has progressed following two or more lines of chemotherapy. Radiological response rates have improved in patients with tumors expressing PD-L1 protein on both tumor and immune cells. Additionally, patients with microsatellite instability (MSI) or mismatch repair deficiency (dMMR) have demonstrated significantly higher radiological response rates and overall survival. There are also tumor-agnostic indications for treating MSI cancers with anti-PD-1 therapy [32]. However, immune checkpoint blockade had limited success in previous lines of

therapy until recently. Other biomarkers, including Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) status and tumor mutational load, are currently under evaluation to identify potential responders to immunotherapy. Moreover, the integration of biomarkers into treatment planning holds the promise of personalizing therapy and improving outcomes for patients with advanced gastric cancer.

7-7. Palliative Care for Patients with Gastric Cancer

Patients with advanced gastric cancer benefit from a comprehensive care approach that extends beyond chemotherapy. Nutritional guidance is essential to minimize avoidable weight loss, and dietary modifications or supplements may be recommended based on individual needs. For tumors causing bleeding, treatment options may include endoscopic coagulation, tranexamic acid, radiotherapy, embolization, or, in rare cases, surgery [33].

Early referral to palliative care services can significantly enhance symptom management and improve the overall quality of life. Importantly, palliative care should be viewed as an integral component of the patient's treatment pathway and is not mutually exclusive with active therapies such as chemotherapy. Additionally, fostering open communication among patients, families, and healthcare providers is crucial for aligning care goals and optimizing support throughout the treatment journey.

8. Conclusion

The challenges of gastric cancer are both epidemiological and therapeutic. The primary goal should be to reduce the incidence of gastric cancer through ongoing public health initiatives, the implementation of endoscopic screening programs in high-risk areas, and the development of new, less invasive tools for early detection. Dietary and lifestyle modifications are among the most effective strategies for preventing gastric cancer, particularly in developed countries. Moreover, advances in genetic testing facilitate early detection and improve survival rates.

A significant challenge lies in translating recent discoveries in molecular biology into effective treatments for patients with gastric cancer. The intra-tumor, intra-patient, and inter-patient heterogeneity observed in gastric cancer poses a critical barrier to the development of targeted therapies. Consequently, further research is essential to comprehend and address these challenges effectively. Ultimately, fostering collaboration across multiple disciplines, including research, clinical practice, and public health, will be vital in improving outcomes for patients with gastric cancer.

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